

Synergy Robotics -AB

Seattle WA 98125 USA.

Dr Bheemaiah, Anil Kumar. Director and Digital Nomad,
bheemaiaha@yopmail.com

The Carcass.

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Abstract: The story of the carcass, a dead shell of an automobile discovered by future humanity in a desert-like Mojave, where they reconstruct a history of living metal bodies automobiles as the residents of this planet. We propose a method to bring to life this carcass with electric hub wheels and autopilot systems and consider the creation of Wall-E inspired LandBots, all for afforestation and many other task automation after the discovery of one living plant. Maybe Earth is habitable again?

Keywords: LandBots, Wall-E, Humour, ELeCtric Wheels, Singularity#1, Taskoids

Overview

I am researching mobility, the evolution of the electric hub motor wheel. It started with an accidental discovery of an electric hub motor for a bicycle. It soon vegetatively reproduced to form the n-cycle, for n++, it soon was multi-mobile. With the discovery of the 'carcass', the body of an automobile in the desert, I wanted to create an open technology project to recycle the carcass, to bring dignity in death, so the resurrection was a hyper design to be printed in carbon composite with a BAAM printer. The design is customizable, The carcass would live with electric hub wheels, any number of them, of any wattage.

Goals

We need the following services:

1. BAAM printing of the chassis free carcass body.
2. Spares stock of Nitrogen filled Hub Motor Wheels

3. **Pre-series fitment of chassis free carcass designs with wheels, upgradable to higher/lower power ratings and better hub motor technologies. OEM integration of spares stock with carcass manufacturing.**

We are planning to bring the carcass to life in the Indian Himalayas, where our team will on the fly rotate and fix hub motors as spares, the customers are democratic left minded stubborn mules, used in Himalayan expeditions since they are left minded, only the state can own the carcass and maintain it, with the private sector breathing life through spares stock and sponsoring trail songs. There is a human to carcass ratio of 1: 10, with an expenditure of \$2000 per human by the government a year to maintain them at high altitude and a population of at least 1,000 people, we are estimating an investment of \$2k * 1000 in the carcass project.

Specifications

The Landbot as a story of resurrection.

The Landbot was defined as a carcass, like a cuboid, with four wheels fitted with a rubber or alloy tracks, a multipurpose MFA II based Singularity#1 Sentient Robot("On Singularity#1" n.d.), with an adaptable toolset.

We consider the accidental discovery of a cuboid chunk of alloy or we may optionally design and print one in carbon composite with fuselages to mount the electric hub motors.

Segway provides stock conversion from its scooter series, especially Max("Ninebot KickScooter MAX" n.d.) of efficient 1.5 KiloWatt batteries and powerful electric wheels with hub motors, we need two wheels with braking and two electric wheels and two mother-boards and a communication board.

We add auto-navigation using VSLAM(Contributors to Wikimedia projects 2004)(Contributors to Wikimedia projects 2014) with cloud functions using an Nvidia Jetson Nano pack and Redtail software.(Contributors to Wikimedia projects 2004; NVIDIA-AI-IOT n.d.)

Tool assemblies can consist of N GeckoBot Vacuum appendages("Website" n.d.) or an off the shelf forklift, or pneumatic drive assemblies with a host of tool accessories, including augers,

3D printers, pneumatic hammers, soil vacuum assemblies and rotary tools with a vast tool bit set.

In a separate paper, we consider the dog-ear interface and the mathematical formulation for Taskoids for various work automation.(Bheemaiah, n.d.)

A cuboid carcass like Wall-E, on a dead planet, is resurrected with Segway max electric wheels and one living plant, maybe a beanstalk?

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